

Knowledge and Practices in TOS-Making of the San Isidro College Faculty

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ABSTRACT

The Table of Specifications (TOS) is a pivotal tool in educational assessment, offering a structured framework for the planning and organization of exams. Despite its potential benefits, a prevalent challenge arises from the need for more understanding of effectively utilizing a Table of Specifications. This lack of coherence leads to a test that cannot give teachers sufficient data to assess students' progress (Brookhart, 2001) accurately. Aligned with the PAASCU recommendation to San Isidro College on teaching and curriculum, the faculty is required to integrate the alignment of TOS into their test-making practices. Consequently, the study aimed to answer (1) what is the level of knowledge among the college faculty in TOS-making, (2) whether there is a significant difference in the level of knowledge in the content and process of TOS based on faculty profiles, (3) what practices do college faculty employ in test-making, and (4) what are the indicators of a practical test? The researchers utilized a mixed-method research design, precisely, a descriptive approach that gathers quantitative and qualitative data. The results revealed that the college faculty at San Isidro College has excellent and high knowledge of the content and process of the Table of Specifications. When grouped according to faculty profiles, no significant differences emerge in the knowledge of content and process of TOS between education and non-education graduates, nor terms of length of service. However, a significant difference exists in the level of knowledge based on different schools. Furthermore, the findings unveil diverse practices college faculty utilize in test-making, accompanied by varied perspectives on what constitutes an adequate test. The findings also underscore the utilization of indicators of a practical exam by school deans to assess the faculty's constructed tests or exams.

Subject Area

TOS Making

Keywords: *table of specifications (TOS); test construction; practices; knowledge*

INTRODUCTION

Assessment is a critical part of the teaching and learning process. Constructing a test, a form of assessment is an essential skill for a 21st-century educator. Teachers should be concerned that the test measures an acceptable sampling of the material covered in class at the cognitive level at which the topic was introduced. To efficiently measure learners' performance in class, teachers follow a comprehensive guide in constructing tests. This guide is referred to as the Table of Specifications.

According to Notar et al. (2004), a table of specification is called a test blueprint that helps teachers align objectives, instruction, and assessment. It assists teachers in determining the kinds of items they should include on their assessments by allowing them to correlate the amount of class time spent on each objective with the cognitive level at which each objective was taught. Every topic or target cannot be measured, and teachers can only sometimes ask all the questions they would like to. A table of specifications enables the teacher to create a test that concentrates on the crucial topics and weights the various topics according to their significance and gives the instructor proof that an exam is valid in terms of content or that it covers the material that should be covered (Chase, 1999).

One significant problem that most teachers encounter is creating valid and reliable questions that measure what they should measure. Due to insufficient knowledge of how to use a table of specifications, some teachers cover specific topics in their lesson plans while others create their own questions; only low-level objectives, such as knowledge and comprehension, are covered. Some sets could be clearer and more complex and repeat the same questions every year for different sets of students, thereby registering poor and unsatisfactory conditions for assessment. This lack of coherence leads to a test that cannot give teachers sufficient data to assess students' progress accurately (Brookhart, 2001).

A study conducted by Rivai et al. (2019) found that the quality of objective tests that are made by the Sociology teachers of Public and Private vocational schools in Jakarta is influenced by teachers' knowledge of test construction, mastery of teaching materials, attitudes toward subject, creativity, perseverance, educational background, motivation, commitment, organizational and management. Ing et al. (2015) also conducted a study that found a need for more knowledge in constructing tests using TOS. Most of the teachers should have referred to the table of specifications while building instruments for assessment. This indicates that teachers need to gain fundamental knowledge in designing a standard table of specifications and are unaware of the importance of the table of specifications.

In San Isidro College, it was recently recommended by the Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges, and Universities (PAASCU) that the college department practice TOS-making to improve the assessment of students' learning. The teachers need to develop a TOS that will guide item construction, which considers the relative importance of each component of the syllabus and each level of the cognitive domain. Hence, this study aimed to assess the level of knowledge in TOS and test-making practices of the college faculty at San Isidro College.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aimed to assess the level of knowledge in TOS-making and test the construction practices/strategies of the college faculty at San Isidro College.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of knowledge among the college faculty in TOS-making?
2. Is there a significant difference between the level of knowledge in the content and process of TOS making and faculty profile when grouped accordingly to:
 - a. education and non-education faculty;
 - b. school; and
 - c. length of service.
3. What are the practices the college faculty apply in test-making?
4. What are the indicators of effective test?

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on the framework proposed by Fives and Barnes (2018) on Classroom Test Construction: The Power of a Table of Specification. The TOS is a valuable instrument in accurately evaluating specific content areas and cognitive abilities intended to be assessed. Its primary objective is to assist teachers in effectively allocating class time for each learning objective and aligning them with the corresponding cognitive levels at which these objectives are taught. Fives and Barnes (2018) posit that the validity of tests is best measured using the Table of Specifications. Hence, the conceptual framework provides a foundation for assessing the knowledge and expertise of college faculty members in TOS-making and test construction. By examining these factors, the study aims to improve assessment practices within the college setting and enhance overall student learning outcomes.

Figure 1 below illustrates the framework of the present study. Knowledge of TOS-making is divided into two components: content and process.

Figure 1.
Schematic Diagram of the Framework of the Study

Content. Content refers to all the essential elements of the TOS. Alade and Omoruyi (2014) enumerated six significant elements that should be included in the preparation of TOS. It includes balance among goals selected for examination, balance among levels of learning, the test format, the total number of items, the number of test items for each goal and level of learning, and the enabling skills to be selected from each goal framework. Fives and Barnes (2018) also stressed that teachers should determine the number of test items to include and the distribution of these items in the taxonomy of learning objectives.

Process. Process refers to the set of steps that need to be done in order to create and design a TOS. The first and most crucial step in making the TOS is identifying the topics covered within a period and their corresponding learning outcomes. The items are then distributed to the different cognitive levels of Bloom’s Taxonomy. Bloom’s Taxonomy is essential because it is a strategic approach to ensure that assessments are well-rounded and cover the full spectrum of cognitive skills (McNulty, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a mixed-method research design, precisely a descriptive approach, to gather quantitative and qualitative data. The researchers gathered quantitative and qualitative data in the same timeframe and with equal weight (Creswell, 2003).

Thirty (30) full-time and part-time instructors were the study's respondents. They belong from the different schools in the college department: the School of Education, the School of Arts and Sciences, the School of Accountancy, the School of Business Administration, the School of Engineering, the School of Nursing, the School of Midwifery, and the School of Information Technology. The study utilized a simple random sampling. The study was conducted in San Isidro College, Impalambong, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, specifically among the instructors in the college department during the Academic Year 2022-2023.

The gathering of data was done both online via Google Forms and face-to-face using a researcher-made questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into three (3) sections: (1) faculty demographic profile, (2) knowledge of TOS, which is composed of content and process, and (3) methods of making TOS. Before conducting the study, the researchers sought experts' advice and approval to ensure the content's validity. The reliability of the questionnaire was tested by conducting a pilot test on ten (10) teachers from other institutions. The reliability test showed that the questionnaire obtained a Cronbach alpha of $\alpha=0.71$, indicating reliability. The demographic profile and the responses regarding TOS provided the quantitative data. The instrument utilized a Likert rating scale, which provides more than two options.

Meanwhile, questions regarding practices in TOS-making gathered the qualitative data. Open-ended questions were provided to accommodate free-formatted views. The responses were coded manually by the researchers and analyzed using thematic analysis.

In assessing the level of knowledge on the content of TOS, a 3-point Likert scale was utilized. The criteria used to assess the responses reflect the scoring procedure in Table 1.

Table 1.
The level of knowledge on the Content of Table of Specifications

Scale	Mean Interval	Description	Interpretation
3	2.33 – 3.00	Knowledgeable	Has good knowledge on the content of Table of Specifications
2	1.67 – 2.32	Moderately Knowledgeable	Has moderate knowledge on the content of Table of Specifications
1	1.00 – 1.66	Not knowledgeable	Has poor knowledge on the content of Table of Specifications

In assessing the level of knowledge on the process of making TOS, a 5-point Likert scale was utilized. The criteria used to assess the responses reflect the scoring procedure in Table 2.

Table 2.
The Level of Knowledge on the Process of making Table of Specifications

Scale	Mean Interval	Description	Interpretation
5	4.51 – 5.00	Very much Knowledgeable	Very high knowledge on the process of making Table of Specification
4	3.41 – 4.20	Much Knowledgeable	High knowledge on the process of making Table of Specification
3	2.61 – 3.40	Knowledgeable	Moderate on the process of making Table of Specification
2	1.81 – 2.60	Moderately Knowledgeable	Low knowledge on the process of making Table of Specification
1	1.00 – 1.80	Not knowledgeable	Very low knowledge on the process of making Table of Specification

The data for the knowledge of the content and process of making TOS was analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically mean and standard deviation. Moreover, an independent-sample t-test was used to compare the knowledge between the education and non-education college faculty. One-way ANOVA was employed in the knowledge of both content and process since there were more than two groups to be compared the school and the number of years teaching.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The overall mean in Table 3 reveals that the college faculty of San Isidro College has good knowledge of the content of the Table of Specifications. Based on the table, item no. 1, states that “the TOS contains the topics covered in class within a period or semester,” garnered the highest mean. This indicates that all the college faculty know that TOS should contain all the topics discussed within the allotted time. This is true to the study of Chase (1999), which states that in designing a TOS, the test questions should be based on the list of course objectives, the topics covered in class, and the amount of time spent on those topics.

However, item no.2, which states that “the TOS indicates the amount of time spent (in hours) on the topics covered,” got the lowest mean. This may be attributed to the time constraints the college faculty faces, such as a packed curriculum, limited instructional time, or external pressures. As a result, they may prioritize completing the curriculum rather than strictly adhering to the time allocations suggested by the Table of Specifications.

Table 3.
The Level of Knowledge on the Content of Table of Specifications

Content	Mean	Std. Dev.	Description
The TOS contains the topics covered in class within a period or semester.	3.00	0.00	Knowledgeable
The total items of the test should be indicated in the TOS.	2.97	0.57	Knowledgeable
The total percentage of each number of items topic is reflected in the TOS.	2.97	0.75	Knowledgeable
There should be more items allocated on the higher cognitive levels (analyzing, applying, and evaluating) than in remembering.	2.93	0.45	Knowledgeable
The number of items per topic is distributed across the different cognitive levels of Bloom's Taxonomy (remembering, analyzing, applying, etc).	2.87	0.43	Knowledgeable
The TOS should indicate the placement of the items across the different cognitive levels.	2.83	0.50	Knowledgeable
The TOS indicates the amount of time spent (in hours) on the topics covered.	2.63	0.72	Knowledgeable
OVERALL	2.89	0.23	Knowledgeable

The overall mean of Table 4 shows that the college faculty of San Isidro College has a high knowledge of the process of making a Table of Specifications. Among the ten processes of the Table of Specifications, "*The first rule in making TOS is to make sure the coverage of my exam is something that I have taught in class*" has the highest mean. According to Chase's study (1999), a TOS helps to align what is taught and what is tested. By ensuring that the exam's content aligns with what was taught, teachers can effectively assess whether students have achieved the desired learning outcomes and simultaneously enhance the validity of the exam.

However, among the processes, the statements "*I make the TOS first before constructing the test questionnaires*" and "*Before producing the final test questionnaires, I will have the TOS checked/reviewed by the Dean of the school or the Vice President for Academic Affairs*" obtained the lowest mean. This result is congruent with the results of Ing et al. (2015), which found that the majority of the teachers did not refer to their TOS in building assessment instruments. Notar et al. (2004) argue that teachers should make use of the TOS not only for the topics covered in class but also for the performance objectives at each level of Bloom's Taxonomy.

The first statement may have been influenced by the teachers' lack of awareness about the benefits of TOS. According to Odiagbe (2016), the lack of practice in TOS-making may be due to the lack of knowledge in TOS due to insufficient training or seminars. They must understand how it can help ensure alignment between instruction and assessment, improve test validity, and enhance student learning. On the other hand, the second statement may be because other schools did not impose submission of TOS before making the exams or because their exam-creation processes differ.

Table 4.
The Level of Knowledge on the Process of Making Table of Specifications

Process	Mean	Std. Dev.	Description
The first rule in making TOS is to make sure the coverage of my exam is something that I have taught in class.	4.93	0.64	Very much Knowledgeable
The questions in the test questionnaire should reflect the different cognitive levels using Bloom's Taxonomy.	4.53	1.22	Very much Knowledgeable
After selecting the topics, I need to determine the testing objectives for each topic area using the six categories of Bloom's Taxonomy (remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating).	4.53	0.81	Very much Knowledgeable
The objectives per topic area should use specific verbs on how I intend to test the students using the Bloom's Taxonomy.	4.50	0.77	Very Much Knowledgeable
In making the TOS, I determine the duration for each content area to determine how many items I should devote for each topic.	4.47	0.77	Very Much Knowledgeable
In determining the number of the items for each topic, I will multiply the percentage allocation for each topic by the total number of items to be constructed.	4.43	1.03	Very Much Knowledgeable
The formula applied to determine percentage allocation of the test items for each of the topics covered is % for a topic = total number of days/hours spent	4.37	1.09	Very Much Knowledgeable
After aligning the TOS to the learning objectives of Bloom's Taxonomy, I need to determine the test types that will accomplish my testing objectives.	4.33	1.06	Very Much Knowledgeable
Before producing the final test questionnaires, I will have the TOS checked/reviewed by the Dean of the school or the Vice President for Academic Affairs.	4.13	1.42	Much Knowledgeable
I make the TOS first before constructing the test questionnaires.	4.13	1.17	Much Knowledgeable
OVERALL	4.44	0.59	Much Knowledgeable

Table 5 presents the comparison between the level of knowledge on the content of the Table of Specifications of the faculty who are Education and non-Education graduates.

Table 5.
Difference between the Education and Non-Education Faculty's Level of Knowledge on the content of Table of Specifications

Category	Mean	Std. Dev.	t	p
Education Faculty	2.95	0.111	1.394	0.117
Non-Education Faculty	2.84	0.309		

**p>0.05

The t-value of the content of the TOS making in Table 5 is 1.394 with a p-value of 0.117 (p>0.05), indicating no significant difference between education and non-education graduates' knowledge on the content of Table of Specifications.

Table 6 presents the comparison between the level of knowledge on the process of making the Table of Specifications of the faculty who are Education and non-Education graduates.

Table 6.
Difference between the Education and Non-Education Faculty's Level of Knowledge on the process of making a Table of Specifications

Category	Mean	Std. Dev.	t	p
Education Faculty	4.60	0.524	1.293	0.207
Non-Education Faculty	4.33	0.621		

**p>0.05

This implies that the educational background or degree obtained by the college faculty does not necessarily result in a substantial variance in their understanding or familiarity with the content and concepts related to TOS. The knowledge on this subject seems to be similar regardless of whether one the t-value is 1.293 with a p-value of 0.207 (p>0.05), indicating no significant difference between education and non-education graduates' knowledge on the process of making Table of Specifications. The findings suggested that the educational background of individuals, whether they have a degree in education or not, does not lead to a statistically significant distinction in their understanding or familiarity with the process of creating a Table of Specifications has a background in education or not. In order to improve their teaching techniques further, some faculty members who did not major in education earned professional education units.

Table 7 presents the comparison of the level of knowledge of the faculty's of knowledge on the content of the Table of specification when grouped by school.

Table 7.
Difference of the Faculty's Level of Knowledge on the Content of Table of Specifications according to School.

School	Mean	Std. Dev.	f	p
School of Engineering	3.00	0.000	7.812	0.000**
School of Nursing	3.00	-		
School of Education	2.95	0.111		
School of Arts and Sciences	2.94	0.104		
School of Business Administration	2.93	0.101		
School of Accountancy	2.79	0.101		
School of Information Technology	2.14			

**p<0.01

In Table 7, the t-value is 7.812 with a p-value of 0.000 (p<0.05), indicating a significant difference between knowledge on the content of the Table of Specifications regarding school. However, due to the lack of respondents, the result may need to be more conclusive.

The nursing and engineering schools achieved the highest means among the eight schools, followed by those for education, the arts and sciences, business administration, accounting, and information technology, respectively. All faculty members from the School of Midwifery have not responded to the survey. The low number of respondents relative to other schools may have contributed to the high mean values reported from the nursing and engineering schools.

Table 8 presents the comparison of the level of knowledge of the faculty's of knowledge on the process of making the Table of specification when grouped by school.

Table 8.

Difference of the Faculty's Level of Knowledge on the process of making a Table of Specifications according to School

School	Mean	Std. Dev.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
School of Arts and Sciences	4.64	0.397		
School of Education	4.60	0.524		
School of Engineering	4.55	0.212		
School of Nursing	4.50	-	2.733	0.000**
School of Business Administration	4.15	1.202		
School of Accountancy	3.75	0.071		
School of Information Technology	3.35	0.354		

**p<0.01

The *f*-value is 2.733 with a *p*-value of 0.037 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a significant difference between knowledge on making a Table of Specifications regarding school. However, due to the lack of respondents, the result may need to be more conclusive. This interpretation suggests that the specific school from which the college faculty comes impacts their understanding or familiarity with creating a Table of Specifications. The results of this study suggest notable differences in knowledge levels among individuals from various schools, indicating that the educational environment or curriculum in different schools may influence their understanding of this process. It is important to remember that the statistical study underlies this interpretation has a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$. To fully comprehend the observed knowledge gaps between people from other schools, though, more research and evaluation of additional elements or variables may be required.

Table 9 presents the comparison of the level of knowledge of the faculty's of knowledge on the content of the Table of specification when grouped by years of teaching.

Table 9.

Comparison on the Level of Knowledge on the Content of Table of Specifications in terms of year teaching.

Years of Teaching	Mean	Std. Dev.	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Below 1 Academic Year	2.93	0.153		
1-3 Academic Years	2.94	0.112	1.913	0.152
4-5 Academic Years	2.57	0.724		
More than 5 Academic Years	2.90	0.127		

**p>0.05

The statistical analysis suggests that no significant difference was conducted, the obtained *t*-value of 1.913, and in knowledge regarding the content of Table the associated *p*-value of 0.152 ($p > 0.05$) of Specifications when considering different years of teaching experience.

This interpretation indicates that the number of years a teacher has been teaching has little effect in their understanding or familiarity with the content of the Table of Specifications. College faculty who taught for 1-3 academic years had the highest mean year-to-year ratio, while those who taught for 4-5 years had the lowest.

It is critical to consider other elements or variables that can impact knowledge levels, such as the professional development or training possibilities teachers have had access to, their

pedagogical strategies, or their exposure to other curricula. To offer a more thorough understanding of the relationship between years of teaching experience and knowledge of the content of the TOS, further investigation and analysis of these elements may be required.

Table 10 presents the comparison of the level of knowledge of the faculty's of knowledge on the process of making the Table of specification when grouped by years of teaching.

Table 10.
Comparison on the Level of Knowledge on the Process of Making Table of Specifications in terms of year Teaching

Years of Teaching	Mean	Std. Dev.	t	p
Below 1 Academic Year	4.74	0.521	1.807	0.171
1-3 Academic Years	4.50	0.702		
4-5 Academic Years	3.90	0.700		
More than 5 Academic Years	4.33	0.479		

**p>0.05

The t-value is 1.807 with a p-value of 0.171 (p>0.05), indicating no significant difference between knowledge on making Table of Specifications regarding year teaching.

The results of the data suggested that there are no significant differences in knowledge levels among teachers with different years of teaching experience when making a Table of Specifications. According to the table above, the mean for teachers with less than one academic year of experience was the greatest, while for teachers with 4-5 years of experience was the lowest.

Frame 1.
Practices in Constructing Exams/ Tests employed by the College Faculty.

Significant Statements	Unit meaning	Formulated Meaning
R1: <i>“Formulate questions based on the objectives of the course.”</i>	Aligned to the Course/Learning Outcomes and Curriculum	The faculty makes sure that the exam is aligned to the Course/Learning Outcomes and Curriculum.
R2: <i>“Make sure that it’s aligned to the curriculum.”</i>		
R3: <i>“I make a simple question but formulate in using suggested stem question by Bloom's Taxonomy.”</i>	Apply Bloom’s Taxonomy	The faculty makes sure to apply Bloom’s Taxonomy.
R4: <i>“I also review the Revised Bloom's Taxonomy and its behavioral verbs.”</i>		
R5: <i>“I used table of specifications and I make sure that the exam I created is aligned to the course objectives.”</i>	Aligned to the Table of Specifications	The faculty makes sure to align the exam to the Table of Specifications.
R6: <i>“I listed first all the coverage for the term...”</i>	Identify and List the Coverage of the Exam	The faculty makes sure to identify and list the Coverage of the Exam
R7: <i>“I usually do list of topics covered in the class then summarize it into small chunks</i>		

where I will derive the test questions for the exam.”

R8: “Determine the test format or type of exam and use variety of question types applying Bloom's Taxonomy.”	Identify the Test Format and Type of Exam	The faculty makes sure to identify the Test Format and Type of Exam
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R9: “I assess and chose test types appropriate to the questions I intend to make.”

The responses found in Frame 1 present the different techniques or methods in constructing exams, which were analyzed qualitatively using thematic analysis. Based on the responses of the college faculty, the following unit meanings were formulated:

1. Aligned to the Course/Learning Outcomes and Curriculum,
2. Apply Bloom's Taxonomy,
3. Aligned to the Table of Specifications,
4. Identify and List the Coverage of the Exam, and
5. Identify the Test Format and Type of Exam.

Based on the frame presented above, we can infer that the college faculty implores various techniques and strategies in constructing exams or tests. One of the formulated meanings indicated that the faculty makes sure that the exam is aligned with the course/learning outcomes and curriculum. This indicates that the college faculty are keen on ensuring that their exams match the curriculum's expected learning outcomes. This is like another unit labeled "Identify and List the Exam Coverage." This unit meaning is relative to the knowledge part in making the Table of Specifications in the questionnaire, which states, "The TOS contains the topics covered in class within a period or semester." The faculty's awareness of making the TOS, specifically on what topics are covered in class, aligns with that of their techniques or methods in constructing tests.

Similarly, the college faculty practice aligning their exam to the Table of Specifications are constructed prior to the making of the exam. This is a good indicator that the faculty in the college department are practicing TOS-making before the test construction. However, there needs to be more consistency in the results when they were asked to answer the second open-ended question. Only nine (9) of the twenty (20) respondents said they referred to their TOS before constructing their exam. The following significant statements were drawn:

"I also know that TOS is meant to ensure alignment and streamlining between curriculum, instruction, and assessment." –R1

"I usually prefer to make the TOS before the exam." –R2

"Yes, I always refer to my TOS when I create an exam. I frequently utilize it beforehand to make sure that all the questions are related to the topics I have covered." –R3

Other responses were also coded and were found to be connected. Based on the results above, the college faculty identify the test format and type of exam when constructing their tests. This method may be related to another unit meaning, which states that the college faculty applies Bloom's Taxonomy to formulate the questions. This is also aligned with their responses in items 4

and 5 in the knowledge of content and items 4 and 7 in the knowledge of the process of making the TOS. Based on Tables 3 and 4, the college faculty displayed good knowledge of these items. Referring to Bloom's Taxonomy for constructing the exams is essential. According to Clotilda (2022), Bloom's Taxonomy provides a clear and structured framework for educators to design learning objectives and outcomes. This framework can help educators develop more effective teaching strategies and assessments that align with the learning goals.

Frame 2.

Summary of the Responses on the Indicators of a Good Exam.

Significant Statements	Unit Meaning	Formulated Meaning
R1: <i>“An effective exam is a well-formulated set of questions that covers the entire goals and objectives of the course which can measure the level of the transfer of learning to the learners.”</i>	Covers the entire goals and objectives of the course	The faculty believes that the exam covers the entire goals and objectives of the course
R2: <i>“An exam should consist items that are measurable and are consistent/relevant with/to the course guide.”</i>		
R3: <i>“An exam can be effective or good if it elicits the true understanding and learning with the topics you have discussed in a course program.”</i>	Elicits the true understanding and learning with the topics discussed in a course program.	The faculty believes that the exam elicits the true understanding and learning with the topics discussed in a course program
R4: <i>“An exam is effective or good when it successfully measured what it ought to measure.”</i>	Alignment in the learning goals/ outcomes and content as stated in the curriculum	The faculty believes that the exam alignment in the learning goals/ outcomes and content as stated in the curriculum
R5: <i>“Everything should align to its core which is the learning outcomes.”</i>		
R6: <i>“Tests should measure the amount of students’ learning after being taught in class.”</i>	Comprehensively covers the topics for the term.	The faculty believes that the exam comprehensively covers the topics for the term
R7: <i>“An exam should mirror everything that transpired in the classroom. It should not include topics that are irrelevant to class.”</i>		
R10: <i>“It has variety of test types applying the bloom's taxonomy in formulating the questions and instructions are clear and comprehensible.”</i>	Measures their problem solving/critical thinking skills.	The faculty believes that the exam measures their problem solving/ critical thinking skills
R11: <i>“It test the problem-solving/critical thinking skills of the students.”</i>		
R12: <i>“It should include HOTS questions that will allow the students to develop or use the 21st century skills in different levels.”</i>		

R1: <i>“An exam should be well-balanced: not too easy, not too difficult. It is not meant to be a piece of cake to students nor would it be a form of punishment.”</i>	Well-balanced: not too easy, not too difficult.	The faculty believes that the exam is well balance: not too easy, not too difficult
R2: <i>“Balance between easy, intermediate, and difficult questions.”</i>		
R3: <i>“When you make Multiple Choice, there must be items that require the students to analyze, apply, and evaluate; not only the knowledge level.”</i>		

Frame 2 presents the responses of the college faculty on the indicators of a good exam. They were analyzed qualitatively using thematic analysis. Based on the frame shown above, the following unit meanings were formulated:

1. Covers the entire goals and objectives of the course
2. Elicits the proper understanding and learning with the topics discussed in a course program
3. Alignment in the learning goals/ outcomes and content as stated in the curriculum
4. Comprehensively covers the topics for the term
5. Measures their problem-solving/critical thinking skills
6. Well-balanced: not too easy, not too difficult

Based on the above results, the college faculty have various perspectives on what makes an exam good. According to them, a good exam should cover all the goals and objectives of the course they are teaching. This also aligns with their responses in Frame 1 on their methods in constructing tests, specifically, “Aligned to the Course/Learning Outcomes and Curriculum.” This is quite similar to another unit meaning formulated, which states that a good exam ensures alignment in the learning goals/ outcomes and content as stated in the curriculum. The college faculty also collectively answered that a good exam should comprehensively cover the topics for the specific term.

Another formulated unit meaning indicates that a good exam should measure their higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), such as their critical and problem-solving skills. This response can be aligned with their answer in Frame 1, which states that Bloom’s Taxonomy should be applied in both TOS and test construction. Hence, their responses under the unit meaning “well-balanced: not too easy, not too difficult.” Employing Bloom’s Taxonomy can help the instructors distribute the items across certain difficulty levels. Thus, avoiding tests that are too difficult or easy for the students. The following statements support this formulated meaning:

“An exam should be well-balanced: not too easy, not too difficult. It is not meant to be a piece of cake to students, nor would it be a form of punishment.” –R1

“When you make Multiple Choice, there must be items that require the students to analyze, apply, and evaluate, not only the knowledge level.” –R2

The results in Frames 1 and 2 are significant in assessing whether their methods or techniques in constructing exams align with their knowledge level in making the TOS.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This study aimed to assess the knowledge of the college faculty in making TOS and test construction. Based on the study's findings, the college faculty have excellent knowledge regarding the content and process involved in TOS-making. A t-test analysis was conducted to compare the knowledge levels of education and non-education graduates. The results indicate that the understanding of the content and process of TOS-making is the same based on the educational background of the college faculty. This means that whether they have an education-related degree or not does not significantly affect their understanding or familiarity with TOS-making.

However, a significant difference was found when the one-way ANOVA analysis was performed to examine the impact of different schools on the faculty's knowledge. This suggests that different schools' educational environments and practices influence the college faculty's understanding of the content and process of TOS-making. On the other hand, the length of service, or the number of years the college faculty members have been teaching, was analyzed. The results show no significant difference in their knowledge of TOS-making based on the length of service. This implies that the amount of teaching experience does not substantially impact their understanding of the content and process involved in TOS-making.

In constructing tests, the college faculty employ various practices such as alignment to the course or learning outcomes and curriculum, application of Bloom's taxonomy, alignment to the TOS, identification of the coverage of the test, and identification of test format and type of test. The college faculty believed that the indicators of a practical test cover the entire goals and objectives of the course, elicit proper understanding and learning with the topics discussed in a course program, and align the learning goals/ outcomes and content as stated in the curriculum, comprehensively covers the topics for the term, measures the problem-solving/critical thinking skills of the students, and designed a well-balanced test that is not too easy and not too difficult.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to assess the knowledge of the college faculty in making TOS and test construction. Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The faculty of San Isidro College has good knowledge of TOS content. In addition, the college faculty has high knowledge of process of TOS-making
2. There is no significant difference in the knowledge of content and process of TOS between education and non-education graduates, nor terms of length of service. However, there is a significant difference in the level of knowledge based on different schools where the college faculty belong.
3. The following are the practices employed by the college faculty in test-making: (1) align to the course or learning outcomes and curriculum, (2) apply Bloom's taxonomy, (3) align to the TOS, (4) identify and list the coverage of the test, and (5) identify test format and type of test.
4. In constructing tests, the following are indicators of practical tests: (1) covers the entire goals and objectives of the course, (2) elicits the proper understanding and learning with the topics discussed in a course program, (3) aligns the learning goals/ outcomes and content as stated in the curriculum, (4) comprehensively covers the topics for the term,

(5) measures the problem-solving/critical thinking skills of the students, and (6) designed a well-balanced test that is not too easy and not too difficult.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. The deans may require the faculty in their respective schools to use TOS to enhance the validity of teacher-made tests and improve student learning.
2. The school administrators may provide the faculty with training and workshops on using assessment tools, including the essential component of a TOS.
3. The college faculty may be encouraged to consistently create valid and reliable questions that accurately measure the intended learning outcomes, enabling an accurate assessment of student's achievement in their program of study.
4. The school deans may use the indicators of a practical exam to assess the faculty's constructed tests or exams.

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